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THE STUDY OF TEMPORAL OCCURRENCE OF LANDSLIDES USING DIGITAL PHOTOGRAMMETRY

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Keywords: Landslide Temporal Evolution Model; Digital Photogrammetry; Digital Elevations Models; Air Photograph

Analyses of temporal occurrence of landslides in recent decades and related landform evolution are often based on the use of air photographs. The use of detailed digital photogrammetric techniques offers the possibility to obtain more precise landslide inventories as well as quantitative data on mass transfer and landform evolution. However, the use of older air photographs (most of them obtained prior to the sixties or seventies) presents different problems. A procedure is presented based on the application of digital photogrammetry to the determination of different morphometric parameters of landslides. Those parameters are used on the one hand as indicators of landslide activity. On the other hand, they provide quite precise data on mass transfer and landform evolution and can therefore be used to quantify the contribution of landslides to relief evolution. The technique presented was developed using a DPW that is compatible with a GIS (Arcview) and a CAD (Microstation). Very precise map representation of landslides and their constituting elements, as well as accurate measurements of morphometric parameters can be obtained. Some of these parameters provide information on landslide activity and could be used for monitoring purposes. Uncertainty in the identification of map limits due to differences in the application of mapping criteria by different operators was reduced by a prior analysis of mapping errors and definition of an "uncertainty buffer" for contacts. Detailed digital stereoscopic models were obtained for each set (flight date) of air photographs using different networks of tie and ground points. From each model a DEM and derivative DTMs were calculated. Landslide maps previously described, were then overlain on the DEM; subsequently 3-D representations of landslides produced during each period analysed were obtained. The accuracy of these "digital landslide 3-D models" can be up to 40 cm in favourable conditions. Comparison between landslide models can then be used to determine denudation or mass transfer during the period between successive flights and rates calculated. The technique described was applied to the analysis of an area on the northern side of the Cantabrian Range. Black and white, colour and infrared air photographs at scales between 1/30,000 and 1/5,000, taken between 1956 and 2002 were used. The results obtained will be presented and the accuracy and errors of the method discussed.

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THE FOSIPIL PROJECT: AN IMPROVEMENT OF THE LANDSLIDE SUSCEPTIBILITY MAPS

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Keywords: Landslide susceptibility maps; Digital Photogrammetry; Landslides; North Spain

Digital photogrammetry technique has been used to analyze the temporal occurrence of recent landslides. The use of past aerial photographs is the most employed method to analyze the recent slope instability. Since ending forties to present it is possible to find aerial photos in the European countries. However, the application of digital photogrammetry technique to antique aerial photos causes different problems. Some of these problems as well as the use of data in the elaboration of landslide temporal evolution models, are discussed in this work. The technique, developed into a Digital Photogrammetric Workstation (DPW), is compatible with a GIS, and give accurate results with respect to all the measures related with the landslide morphometrical parameters, included its mapping. These parameters give out important information about the landslide state of activity. The criteria used to delimit de landslide area, and the morphometrical slope parameters were defined by means of an expert analysis, in order to erase the typical cartographic errors due to identification and mapping. The methodological approach proposed in this work is applied in a small mountain area in the Cantabrian Region (Northern Spain). Four photographic flights: 1970, at 1/20.000 scale and in black and white (b/w); 1985, at 1/15.000 scale and in color (co); 2001, at 1/20.000 scale (co) and 2003, at 1/5.000 scale, (co) and infrared (Ir) have been used to obtain a landslide temporal evolution model. Different tie and ground points were designed in order to obtain accurate digital stereoscopic models from each flight. DEM models were created and edited; derivative DTMs were obtained. Landslide features were mapping, in each flight, using the digital stereoscopic models, into DPW, applying the previous cartographic criteria. Using all these information, a landslide temporal occurrence model was obtained and a slope evolution model was proposed. The most important errors due to the improper use of the traditional methods are compared with the results obtained from the digital approach proposed; all of these are described and analyzed.

The FODISPIL project: An improvement in landslide susceptibility maps

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1. INTRODUCTION

Mass movements are slope processes controlled by gravity and they occur in all geomorphological areas and climatic zones. Mass movements are an important geomorphological process and their development is a potential threat for human lives and assets. In Spain, mass movements constitute the third most serious geomorphological hazard (Díaz de Terán et al., 1997), with losses for 1986-2016, estimated by Ayala et al. (1987), expected to reach 7.6×10^9 US dollars. It is thus important to design and implement measures to mitigate the hazard they represent. One of the most useful tools to mitigate the development of this type of process is the elaboration of susceptibility, hazard and risk maps (UNDR0, 1991). However, the elaboration of such maps is not a simple task, due to the complexity of these phenomena and the difficulty in properly assessing their future behaviour. The techniques to elaborate hazard and susceptibility maps have shown a remarkable development in the last forty years thanks to an ever-increasing knowledge of the geologic processes (conditioning and triggering factors), the understanding of their temporal occurrence, and the development of scientific tools such as GIS, Remote Sensing, and the use of statistical techniques. However, despite these advances, hazard and susceptibility maps have spatial

uncertainties that determine the reliability of the final results. Such uncertainties are the result of deficiencies in the mapping of conditioning factors such as, for example:
 - The use of a geomorphological map with either inaccuracies or mistakes in the landslide limits.
 - The use of landslide zones without taking into account the inner geomorphological features.
 - The use of hydrological models with a deficient identification of runoff ways, accumulation zones and volumes.
 - The use of lithological maps either with the lithological unit characterised at an inappropriate scale or without the support of detailed lithological and sedimentological studies (type of materials, sizes, clay fabrics, thickness, textures, type of landslide deposits, etc.).
 - The use of no data on the spatial distribution of the geological structures (including failures, stratum, etc.).
 - The use of no geotechnical information (cohesion, internal friction angle, Atterberg limits, humidity, etc.).
 - The use of no climatic variables (rainfall rate, solar energy, infiltration, etc.).
 There also exist other types of uncertainties relative to the use of inappropriate

digital elevation models (DEM) that characterise the slope geometry, such as for example:
 - use of low precision DEMs obtained from remote sensing data captured either from large range sensors or from projects with low spatial resolution scales,
 - use of DEMs without any field checking measure,
 - use of DEMs with blunders (false line curves, unfiltered infrastructures, buildings and woodland areas),
 - use of high spatial resolution DEMs without any reliability analysis.
 The arrival of digital photogrammetry has led to great progress in connection with the previous signal problems. With the incorporation of this technique into the landslide susceptibility analysis it is now possible to obtain either reliable digital models or precise information about the landslide conditioning factors, and even to make accuracy maps about inner landslide geomorphological features and other natural and/or anthropic elements (Chandler, 2000). In this work, the previous results obtained in the project FODISPIL ("La aplicación de la fotogrametría digital al análisis de la susceptibilidad y peligrosidad de los procesos de inestabilidad de laderas" with financial support from the Ministerio de Ciencia y Tecnología of Spain) on the use of digital photogrammetry techniques to develop precise landslide susceptibility maps are presented.

Fig 1.1. Slope affected by shallow landslides. The red window shows a detail of a landslide with a high resolution lens.

Fig 1.2. Detail of a shallow landslide with a high resolution lens.

Fig 1.3. DPW, Leyca LH-System with LPS.

2. METHODOLOGY

3. RESULTS

The definition of a reliable coordinate system is capital in photogrammetry. This system can be determined by means of ground points measured in the case study and surrounding areas. Geodetic vertices from EUREF net were used. The points measured can be expressed by either their local or WGS84 coordinates. A mesh of control ground points were measured to build up the photogrammetrical model. A large number of additional ground points were measured in order to validate the DEM. All types of images (positive, contact prints, panchromatic films, infrared films, etc.) with overlapped scenes will be used to construct a DEM. These images can be taken either by close range or long range sensors (ground devices, airplanes, satellites, etc.). These images are treated in a Digital Photogrammetric Workstation (DPW). The absolute orientation of the images is obtained using control ground points measured with GPS and total topographical stations. Using DPW, a DEM is obtained measuring a high pixel density of the stereoscopic model. The preliminary DEM is edited in order to delete mistake points, adjusting the DEM points to their right stereoscopic position. The spatial uncertainty of the landslide limits can be reduced by means of buffer limits defined over the basis of Delphy surveys. The Landslide zones can be redefined using the spatial distribution of the landslide geomorphological features. All types of features can be identified in panchromatic images as well as infrared. Anthropical and natural features can be photo-interpreted by means of the stereoscopic models. The features identified in the images can be accurately mapped in the DPW. The 3-D resulting vectors, belonging to different time flights can be compared.

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IDENTIFICATION OF LATENT FAULTS USING A RADON TEST

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Keywords: Radon; Latent faults; Test; Spain; Hazard Analysis

This paper discusses about the use of radon concentration in water of natural springs as a method to identify latent faults in low-mid term activity areas. The identification of this type of active faults may be crucial in hazard analysis. The test used to identify these faults is based on the measure of radon concentration in water, on springs linked with faults, and its comparison with reference value. The radon reference value is obtained through the similar measures made in springs not linked with faults that are distributed around the study area. The positive values obtained from that difference are considered as anomalies that indicate those springs linked with latent faults. The test was applied and validated in spring samples located in Cantabria, Northern Spain. The sample from natural springs was divided in two groups, springs linked with faults and not linked. All the springs analysed are not seasonal and all of them are distributed around the region. Two of the faults sampled, the "Franja Cabaigante de El Escudo de Cabuérniga" fault and the "Selaya-Arredondo" fault, have evidence of a latent behaviour. Furthermore, their springs have thermal waters and seismic and geomorphological evidences of recent tectonic activity. Water samples for each spring were analysed in two sampling campaigns, and alpha and beta total activities and the ^{222}Rn concentration were determined for each sample. The measuring techniques employed were gamma spectrometry with Ge detector, the counting with gas flow proportional counter, and the counting with ZnS(Ag) scintillating detector. Result shows that the test has high validity and specificity. The springs with radon anomalies are located on two latent faults whereas the springs with low radon water concentration are located at the inactive faults.

The use of a test based on the radon concentration in water to identify active faults in areas of mid-low seismic activity

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INTRODUCTION

One of the points that researchers into risk analysis (seismic, land instability, etc.) focus their attention on is the identification of possible active faults. This difficulty may be crucial in those areas of the Earth's crust that can be considered stable from a seismic point of view. However, the development of more than 10 earthquakes located in continental stable areas of North America, Australia and India [1] all of which were associated to faults that were considered as non-active; and had magnitudes over 6.0 and produced surface ruptures, introduced some complications in the definition of such stable areas. All these faults show broad temporal amplitude of the seismic cycle of steps accumulation and release, which imply a slow long-term slip rate on the fault plane [2]. In this sense, the identification of these faults that are in a "latent state" requires additional information.

One of the indicators used to forecast earthquakes are the changes in oxygen isotope ($\delta^{18}O$) contained in ground waters and in the rock water (D/H) [3,4]. Although the origin and mechanism of observed radon anomalies and their relationship to earthquakes is still poorly understood [5], the radon anomaly model proposed by Scholz, et al. [6] makes it possible to give acceptable explanations to those relationships, and to use that anomaly as a possible indicator of active faults, in areas of mid-low seismic activity.

As is known, radon-222 (^{222}Rn) is produced in the decay chain starting with the uranium-238 (^{238}U) and has a half-life of around 4 days. Obviously, the presence of this isotope in the water is derived from the interaction between the rocks and waters that flow through its pores and open fractures.

Different physical and chemical mechanisms control the radon concentration in water (ionic interaction, radon reactions, etc.), all of these are conditioned by variables such as pressure, temperature, PH, contact time between water and rock. So, when the water is in contact with the rock pores the radon is liberated and then released when the waters reach the earth's surface [15,16,17].

Changes in meteorological and seasonal features could modify the radon concentration in waters of soils and intermittent springs [18,19]. However, studying the seasonal variations of radon concentration in waters of Spanish spas, the volume of which waters is constant (deep springs), no significant evidence has been found in the majority of the samples analyzed [14,19]. Another type of change in the radon concentration in water occurs during a seismic cycle [20], which suggests an increase in mechanical crack growth rate or changes in flow rate of groundwater as being responsible for enhancing the radon concentration in waters [13].

In mid-low term activity areas, in which there are continuous tectonic stresses, which could develop seismic movements, the release of radon could be constant. This situation can be good to indicate the faults with a latent behaviour. From a geological point of view the rocks with a chemical composition that may include ^{238}U and/or other members of its decay chain such as, for instance, the ^{232}Th , usually have waters with high ^{222}Rn concentration. The presence of these types of rocks (susceptible rocks) will be either in superficial environments or in deep zones. In the case of these being waters with high ^{222}Rn concentrations and no susceptible rocks in superficial zones, it is assumed that the ^{222}Rn has come from susceptible rocks located in deep geological environments. If it is so, the waters run out quickly, obviously through open cracks that let out high water volumes. These types of structures match up with active faults. In this case, the presence of springs linked to faults with high ^{222}Rn water concentrations should be considered as an indicator of the fault activity. The question is whether the value of ^{222}Rn concentrations measured in normal (and corresponds with the typical emanation values that belong to superficial rocks) or an anomaly (an increment of typical emanation values with ^{222}Rn that has come up from deep zones).

There is a relationship between the mineral composition of rocks and the ^{222}Rn concentration

in waters corresponding to springs and holes bored in those rocks [20,21,22]. Often, aquifers made up by rock types (gneisses, granites, pegmatites, acid volcanic rocks and acid gneisses, etc.) that have enhanced uranium content (higher than 5 ppm) hold a high radon concentration in water, with typical values higher than 50 Bq/L. Sedimentary rocks (limestones, sandstones and shales, as well as igneous, volcanic intermediate and basic rocks) and soils usually have radon concentrations in water between 5 and 70 Bq/L. However, there are rare exceptions in which being tectonic to sedimentary rocks have a high radon concentration. In such instances the water is in contact with uranium mineralizations, contained either in the sediments or filling fault planes that could contribute to the original radon concentration in water increasing.

Taking into account the previous considerations, a chemical test has been proposed to identify potentially active faults in areas of mid-low seismic activity, based on the measurement of ^{222}Rn concentration in waters of springs related with faults, and then comparing the measurements to a reference value. The values that show an excess of radon are considered as anomalies, or indicators of areas of seismic activity.

In order to validate the test, a collection of water samples was taken in different geological environments; all of these were selected in Cantabria (North of Spain). Some samples correspond to inactive areas, from a seismic point of view, others are located on latent faults.

This paper discusses about the use of radon concentration in water of natural springs as a method to identify faults with a latent behaviour. To do that, what is proposed is a test based on the radon concentration in water in order to identify the possible latent faults.

METHODOLOGY

Hypothesis: the springs related to the "latent fault" must register high ^{222}Rn concentration in waters. Obviously the excess of radon arrives from deep areas through open cracks.

Fig. 1. Upper: Cantabria is placed in the northern part of the Cantabrian range. The climate is mild and humid, the average temperature is 14°C at the coast and 10°C in the upper parts of the range. The average annual precipitation is 1200 mm at the coast and over 1600 mm near the mountain divide. Lower: Spatial distribution of population of springs studied.

RESULTS

The water samples analyzed correspond to 47 non seasonal springs (Table 1, Figure 2 and 3). The springs were divided into two groups. Group A comprises the data for 24 springs (Table 2) and corresponds to those springs that are linked with faults. Group B contains the remaining 23 springs (none of which are linked with faults (Table 3)). There is no correlation between total alpha and beta activities and radon concentration in water (Figure 4). Although the samples correspond to lithologies with low concentrations of alpha radiation issuing element, all of them give values that are moderately high in comparison with those of probability reference for radioactivity of the waters [23].

The values of ^{222}Rn concentration in water, for all samples, show measurements between its detection limit (2 Bq/L) and 824 Bq/L (Table 4), with a mean value around 44.3 Bq/L.

Obtaining the reference value

The 23 springs included in B group, shows values of ^{222}Rn concentration in water between its detection limit and 33 Bq/L (Table 3). There are no values higher than ^{222}Rn concentration in water (44.3 Bq/L, even the spring number 42 (located on the lower Triassic sandstones). The values measured are coherent with those proposed by Akérbom and Lindgren [22] for sedimentary materials located in Sweden, which are between 10 and 50 Bq/L. So, it is reasonable to propose the limit of 50 Bq/L as a reference value for the lithologies of the Cantabrian region.

Test validation

The 24 springs included in A group (Table 2), were used to validate the test proposed. The mean value for A group is around 80 Bq/L, which is notably higher than the reference value. This group was divided into two. Subgroup A1 corresponds to the springs linked with faults that have a latent behaviour; subgroup A2 are the springs linked with the remaining faults missed in the territory.

All the springs of A1 subgroup have values of ^{222}Rn concentration in water registered between 24 and 824 Bq/L, with a mean value of 311 Bq/L (Table 5). All springs except number 2 have ^{222}Rn concentrations over and above the reference value. The springs analyzed are linked with the "Frete Cabalgante de El Escudo de Cabuérniga" and "Selaya-Arredondo" faults (Figure 2 and 3). There is geomorphological and sedimentological evidence that allows us to identify these two faults as failures with a latent behaviour [24]. All the springs of A2 subgroup have values of ^{222}Rn concentration in water between its detection limit and 80 Bq/L (Table 5). There is no registered geomorphological and sedimentological evidence of the seismic activity of any of these faults during the upper Pleistocene and Holocene, and neither are there historical relationships between epicenters and springs.

The water temperature values registered in the springs give additional information about the fault behaviour (Table 1). All springs linked to latent faults show high water temperature values. This fact could be explained if the faults had a high permeability due to opened rupture planes, which let out deep origin waters (Table 3).

In order to analyze the validity of this test a first step was to separate some of the springs of A group. Springs 17, 30 and 40 (linked with the Keuper clays) have been discarded, because their lithologies are formed by debris eroded from materials of the hercynian range (Permian granodiorites that contain ^{238}U decay chain elements).

DISCUSSION

Despite the good results obtained with the test proposed, there are values that must be studied in detail and explained in order to detect possible defects in the test. The first question to set out is why there is no correlation between the total alpha and beta activities and the radon concentration in water? As is known, the alpha and beta activities are measured by means of the solid residual dissolved in the water, whereas the radon concentration is measured through the radon gas dissolved in water; these two materials have different ways of dissolving, as well as two different measuring methods. So it is difficult to correlate the measurements for each.

A second question is why spring number 2, linked to the active fault "Frete Cabalgante de El Escudo de Cabuérniga" (Figure 2), has a low radon concentration in water (24 Bq/L) and a high water temperature (35 °C)? This may be due to the fact that spring number 27, linked to the same active fault, at 10 m west of there, has the maximum water radon concentration (824 Bq/L) but a similar water temperature (37 °C). In the case of spring number 2, the sample of water analyzed was taken into a water tank built into a spa, but not at the rise zone. There are reasonable indicators that allow us to say that the water of this spring is being diluted with another coming from a nearby well. The latter, is heated for the thermal purposes of the spa. This would explain the low radon concentration in water and its acceptable temperature.

A similar situation is located at springs number 28 and 23. Another different situation is found at spring 23. In this case the sample points are located not in a spa but in its courtyard. In this case, the relatively low radon concentration and temperature registered in the water could be explained by a natural solution.

A final question is why spring numbers 5, 7, and 37 are linked or not with latent faults. There is not seismic information registered that allow us to state that. However, the attitudes of the three fault planes (NNE-SSW) linked with these springs are coherent with the attitudes of the stress model proposed for this area of the Iberian Peninsula. Those orientations are expected to be unstable under the horizontal shortening (NNE-SSW) registered in the Iberian Peninsula in the Quaternary. Furthermore, from a geomorphological point of view these lineations are clearly evident in the relief by means of linear valleys, with steep slopes and narrow bottomed valleys, that indicates areas where the relief is rejuvenated. Even so, it is still early to verify if those faults have a latent behaviour.

#	Name	Coordinates (UTM)	Altitude (m)	Temperature (°C)	Radon (Bq/L)	Alpha (Bq/L)	Beta (Bq/L)	Notes
1	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
2	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
3	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
4	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
5	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
6	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
7	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
8	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
9	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
10	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
11	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
12	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
13	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
14	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
15	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
16	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
17	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
18	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
19	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
20	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
21	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
22	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
23	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
24	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
25	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
26	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
27	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
28	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
29	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
30	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
31	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
32	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
33	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
34	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
35	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
36	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
37	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
38	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
39	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
40	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
41	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
42	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
43	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
44	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
45	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
46	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21
47	San Pedro	421848,243	479671,685	6.79	6.19	2.0	0.1	21

#	Name	Radon (Bq/L)	Temperature (°C)
1	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
2	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
3	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
4	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
5	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
6	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
7	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
8	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
9	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
10	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
11	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
12	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
13	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
14	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
15	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
16	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
17	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
18	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
19	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
20	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
21	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
22	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
23	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
24	San Pedro	6.19	6.79

#	Name	Radon (Bq/L)	Temperature (°C)
1	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
2	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
3	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
4	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
5	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
6	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
7	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
8	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
9	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
10	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
11	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
12	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
13	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
14	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
15	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
16	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
17	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
18	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
19	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
20	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
21	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
22	San Pedro	6.19	6.79
23	San Pedro	6.19	6.79

Parameter	Value
Mean	44.3
Max	824
Min	2
Std. Dev.	204.5
Total points	47
Mean	44.3

Group	Spring	Radon (Bq/L)	Temperature (°C)
Group A	1	6.19	6.79
	2	6.19	6.79
	3	6.19	6.79
	4	6.19	6.79
	5	6.19	6.79
	6	6.19	6.79
	7	6.19	6.79
	8	6.19	6.79
	9	6.19	6.79
	10	6.19	6.79
	11	6.19	6.79
	12	6.19	6.79
	13	6.19	6.79
	14	6.19	6.79
	15	6.19	6.79
	16	6.19	6.79
	17	6.19	6.79
	18	6.19	6.79
	19	6.19	6.79
	20	6.19	6.79
	21	6.19	6.79
	22	6.19	6.79
	23	6.19	6.79
	24	6.19	6.79

CONCLUSIONS

The results obtained in this work are optimistic. The measurement of radon concentration in water combined with water temperature produces good results that are coincident with the implicit hypothesis contained in this paper. However, it is necessary to resolve some of the uncertainties detected in the sample points previously discussed.

A way to reinforce the method used in this work is to measure ^{226}Ra concentration in the water in addition to the ^{222}Rn and water temperature. The ^{226}Ra can pass a chemical behaviour characterized by its remarkable mobility, either under reducing or oxidizing conditions. The waters from deep origin that make their way out through fault planes could go in contact with uranium mineralizations that cover the fault plane. In this case these waters show high ^{226}Ra concentrations, independent of the fact that they may be combined with other of superfacial origin. So, measuring these variables simultaneously could indeed improve the test proposed.

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Fig. 2

11-6 Oral Remondo, Juan

QUANTITATIVE LANDSLIDE RISK MAPPING ON THE BASIS OF RECENT PAST OCCURRENCES

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Keywords: landslides; risk mapping; hazard modelling; vulnerability assessment; GIS

A quantitative procedure for landslide risk mapping considering both hazard and vulnerability is presented. The approach has been applied in the lower Deva valley (Guipúzcoa, northern Spain) where a detailed study of landslide occurrences and damages in the recent past (last five decades) has been carried out. Statistical analyses and mapping have been implemented on a GIS. Firstly, a susceptibility model was elaborated using an approach based on statistical relationships between past landslides and terrain parameters related to instability factors. Susceptibility (spatial probability) was transformed into hazard (temporal-spatial probability) maps on the basis of frequency, run-out distance and magnitude of past landslides. Scenarios of future behaviour were thus defined. Extrapolations to calculate future probability were made on the basis of trends derived from occurrences during the last 50 years; several scenarios were defined, corresponding to different probability levels. Secondly, a detailed inventory of direct damages due to landslides during the study period was carried out and the main exposed elements in the area identified and mapped. Past direct losses (monetary) per type of element were estimated and expressed as average "specific loss" for events of a given magnitude. Once "specific loss" was calculated, vulnerability was assessed by comparing it with the actual value of the element. Vulnerability thus obtained is expressed as a fraction of total monetary value (0-1 scale). Indirect losses cannot be represented in map form; they were estimated from potential disruption of people and goods flows in the area and expressed numerically. Finally, combination of hazard, vulnerability and monetary value of the different types of elements provided a risk map, expressed in terms of expected direct losses per pixel for a given time span (€/pixel/year), plus indirect losses.

07-6 Oral Bonachea, Jaime

CRITERIA AND INSTRUMENTS FOR THE EVALUATION OF SUSTAINABILITY OF HUMAN MODIFICATION OF SOME GEOMORPHOLOGIC RESOURCES AND ASSETS

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Keywords: visual landscape, sustainability, geomorphologic resources

The general concept of sustainability is widely known and accepted. However, there are difficulties to translate that concept into procedures that can be routinely applied in different realms, such as use or modification of geomorphologic processes or resources. The development of such procedures requires: a) establishment of sustainability criteria; b) identification of indicators that could be used to express criteria; c) design of methods and models for the assessment of sustainability, based on the application of criteria and indicators above; d) development of instruments or tools that can be easily incorporated into standard practice. A key aspect is the identification of suitable indicators that should be, whenever possible, of a quantitative nature. If quantitative indicators are available, thresholds can unambiguously be defined and norms established concerning what can be considered acceptable, sustainable practice.

A proposal is presented for the application of procedures for assessing sustainability in relation to the use of one type of geomorphic resource (surface deposits) and asset (visual landscape). Technological, simulation tools are also developed and their application demonstrated.

For surface deposits the criterion proposed is that exploitation should ensure their availability during a period long enough to make it very likely that technological development will enable the substitution of those materials. Exploitation rate is therefore the criterion used. Application by means of simple-to-implement GIS tools is illustrated. The procedure is particularly suitable for application to administrative jurisdictions responsible for regulation of this activity.

Sustainability criteria for visual landscape are more difficult to establish. One criterion proposed is comparison between the dimensions of "new landforms" (structures, excavations, accumulations) and natural landforms of roughly similar geometric shape (valleys, crests, hills, etc). Average vertical section of landforms is the indicator used. A second criterion is the magnitude and intensity of visual effects produced by new structures. Indicators of magnitude are visibility area and viewing population. Intensity is measured through degree of contrast between new structures and their surroundings. A simulation tool has been developed to measure and assess those visual effects. Its application to the definition of sustainability thresholds will be shown through a case study.

CRITERIA AND INSTRUMENTS FOR THE EVALUATION OF SUSTAINABILITY OF HUMAN MODIFICATION OF SOME GEOMORPHOLOGIC RESOURCES AND ASSETS

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INTRODUCTION

The general concept of sustainability is widely known and accepted. However, there are difficulties to translate that concept into procedures that can be routinely applied in different realms, such as use or modification of geomorphologic processes or resources. The development of such procedures requires: a) establishment of sustainability criteria; b) identification of indicators that could be used to express criteria; c) design of methods and models for the assessment of sustainability, based on the application of criteria and indicators above; d) development of instruments or tools that can be easily incorporated into standard practice. A key aspect is the identification of suitable indicators that should be, whenever possible, of a quantitative nature. If quantitative indicators are available, thresholds can unambiguously be defined and norms established concerning what can be considered acceptable, sustainable practice. The procedure proposed here is illustrated through its application to the analysis of two types of resources: a) consumable, non-renewable (sand and gravel deposits); b) consumable assets subject to damage (visual landscape). The first example considers the effect on non-renewable resource availability of the establishment of protected areas (where exploitation would be banned). The second example deals with the visual impact of new large structures.

Consumable resources

Case study: effect of protected areas on geomorphologic resource availability in the province of Guipúzcoa (Basque country, Spain).

Sustainability criterion: annual rate of extraction should represent a small proportion of total reserves (use of resource ensured during a period long enough to allow substitution).

Indicator: consumption rate compared to reserves.

Assessment procedure and tools: a digital database composed of different thematic layers stored in a GIS was used. Layers selected for analysis were: surface deposits, regolith thickness, protected areas (Fig. 1a, b, c).

Figure 1a. Surface deposits map.

Figure 1b. Regolith thickness map.

Figure 1c. Natural protected areas map.

Total volume	215 x 10 ⁶ m ³
Volume in protected areas	22 x 10 ⁶ m ³ (~10 % of total)
Annual rate of aggregate consumption in the province	8 ton/person/year
Population	670,000 inhabitants
Total consumption	5.4 x 10 ⁶ ton/year

Table 1

About 50% of surface deposits volume can actually be used as aggregate. On the other hand, a similar proportion of aggregates used are obtained from crushed rock. This means that remaining reserves within the province would last no more than 40 years at the present rate of consumption. The alternative is obviously substitution by more crushed rock or through imports from other areas. In other words, the present situation is not sustainable for more than a few decades. However, existing alternatives would imply acceptable cost increases. The quantitative impact on non-renewable resources of creating new protected areas is therefore not very relevant in this context (equivalent to 4 years consumption).

Figure 2a. Total deposit volume map.

Total deposit volume (Fig. 2a) and volume within protected areas (Fig. 2b) were obtained by overlay. Results are shown in Table 1.

Figure 2b. Total deposit volume in protected areas map.

Visual Landscape

Case study: visual impact of a new motorway in the province of Guipúzcoa (Basque country, Spain).

Sustainability criterion: magnitude and intensity of visual effects produced by new structures should be "socially acceptable".

Indicators: indicators of magnitude are visibility area and viewing population. Intensity is measured through degree of contrast between new structures and their surroundings.

Assessment procedure and tools: different thematic layers were used as starting point. DTM: Digital Terrain Model of the zone; GM: Geometry of the Motorway; PD: Areas in the zone classified according to Population Density; RB: Areas, classified according to their proximity to other roads (Road Buffers); LU: Landscape Units.

CSVI (SVI's centroids) can be considered as representative VIEWPOINTS of the zones from which the observation of the motorway proves to be more traumatic on the landscape; they belong to zones of higher population or passerby density (maximum MAGNITUDE), while CMSLU centroids represent road stretches in zones of high scenic value (biggest INTENSITY).

A simulation of results can be attained automatically considering all the realistic visualizations that arise from considering centroid in MSLU as a Target Point and all centroids in SVI as Viewpoints from which the corresponding visualizations are generated (Fig. 3a, b).

Figure 3a. Existing landscape.

Figure 3b. Simulated landscape.

Realistic Views (RV) are simulated, considering the centroids of SVI as viewpoints and centroids of motorway sectors (CMSLU) as view targets (Fig. 4a, b). Intensity of visual intrusion is determined quantitatively (percent of view occupied by the new structure) and qualitatively (generation of a series of RV with different levels of visual intrusion, to define ranks by visual comparison). With this procedure, a limited number of SVI are defined for each motorway sector. A significant advantage of this method is that only a limited "sample" of representative viewing points and view targets must be used to represent the effect over the whole area. The number of RV to be generated is also limited, thus simplifying the assessment of intensity of impacts

Figure 4a. Existing landscape.

Figure 4b. Simulated landscape.

Sustainability assessment: "Sustainability" from the point of view of visual landscape can be assessed by comparison with the magnitude of visual effects of existing structures (also expressed as km² persons) or with a parameter related to the intensity of visual intrusion. This parameter is the "Average Vertical Section" (AVS= H*L) of the structure, compared to that of natural landforms of similar geometric shape (crests and/or valleys in the case of a motorway) (Fig. 5). New structures can be considered a "visually sustainable" if they have: a) a "magnitude of visual effect" lower than that of already existing structures; and b) an AVS < 0.5 of natural landforms of similar shape in the area.

Figure 5. Example of AVS.

CONCLUSIONS

The procedure described expresses changes in geomorphic resources in quantitative terms. Thresholds can thus be established to define what is considered as "sustainable", even in the case of qualities of a "diffuse" nature such as visual quality. Criteria, indicators and procedure proposed can be easily implemented through the use of the technological tools illustrated.

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